

Ferrocene Derivatives. Part-II. Synthesis of some Ferrocenyl[semicarbazone, 1,2-benzodiazepines, cyclohexenone, tetrazolopyrimidine and pyrazolopyrimidine] as Antimicrobial Agents

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Manuscript received 23 February 1987, revised 28 October 1987, accepted 4 November 1987

Acetylferrocene (1) undergoes condensation with semicarbazide hydrochloride and aromatic aldehydes to give the semicarbazone (2) and the α,β -unsaturated ketones (3). Michael condensation of 3a with cyclohexanone, α -tetralone, acetophenone and 1,3-diphenylacetone gives the 1,5-dicarbonyl compounds (4, 5, 10) and the ferrocenylcyclohexenone (11). 1,5-Dicarbonyl compound (4) undergoes condensation with hydrazines to give the 1,2-diazepines (6, 8). Condensation of 3a with 5-aminotetrazole and/or 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole gives the pyrimidotetrazole (12) and pyrimidopyrazole (13). The structures of the hitherto unknown ring systems have been confirmed by analytical and spectral methods.

AS a further extension of our studies¹ on ferrocene in order to obtain compounds with expected biological activity, we report in this paper the results of the reaction of acetylferrocene with semicarbazide hydrochloride, aromatic aldehydes, and the condensation of the α,β -unsaturated ketones with some ketones and aminoazoles.

Acetylferrocene (1) afforded the semicarbazone (2) (Table 2).

In a previous paper¹, we reported the formation of the α,β -unsaturated ketones (3a-c). The addition of cyclohexanone or α -tetralone to 3a in presence of alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution afforded a new series of 1,5-dicarbonyl compounds, namely, 2-[3-oxo-1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-(1-ferrocenyl)]cyclohexanone (4) and 2-[3-oxo-1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-(1-ferrocenyl)]tetralone (5) (Table 2).

1,5-Dicarbonyl compound (4) reacts with hydrazines in presence of acetic acid to yield the corresponding 1,2-diazepines. The reaction of hydrazine with 4 in presence of ethanol and acetic acid, may lead to two cyclic products, namely, 6 and 7 as

inferred from the presence of absorption band at 1730 cm^{-1} (COCH_3) and no absorption due to NH (Table 2). Previous work³ on the reaction of 1,5-dicarbonyl compounds with a bulky group like naphthyl instead of ferrocene favours structure 6 for the products. Similarly it was shown that 4 when reacted with phenylhydrazine afforded two cyclic products, namely, 8 and 9 (Table 2).

Michael condensation of 3a with acetophenone and/or 1,3-diphenylacetone gave the 1,5-dicarbonyl compound (10) and the cyclohexenone derivative (11).

In connection with the above successful reaction, it seemed of interest to react 3a with 5-aminotetrazole, and 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole to obtain the pyrimidotetrazole (12) and pyrimidopyrazole (13). The ir spectra of 12 and 13 are in agreement with the proposed structures. No absorptions due to CO or NH were noticed, and instead a clear and sharp band at $1600-1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) (Table 2) was observed.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Gallenkamp electric melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalyses of carbon and hydrogen were determined at Microanalytical Laboratory, Faculty of Science, University of Mansoura. Ir spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer. ^1H nmr spectra were determined on a Varian T-60 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula (Mol. wt.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				O	H	N
2	85	185	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ FeO (285.117)	55.1 (54.75)	5.1 (5.30)	14.62 (14.73)
4	60	150	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ FeO ₂ (444.327)	70.4 (70.27)	6.4 (6.35)	—
5	65	>300	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ FeO ₂ (492.367)	73.32 (73.17)	5.61 (5.72)	—
6	50	88	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ FeO ₂ (432.387)	69.49 (69.71)	6.31 (6.26)	5.92 (5.80)
8	55	160	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ FeO ₂ (558.477)	73.45 (73.11)	6.01 (6.13)	5.21 (5.01)
10	68	>300	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ FeO ₂ (466.337)	72.43 (72.11)	5.50 (5.62)	—
11	70	>300	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ FeO ₂ (538.437)	77.89 (78.06)	5.7 (5.61)	—
12	56	>300	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ FeO (487.357)	71.63 (71.46)	4.93 (5.17)	8.93 (8.62)
13	51	>300	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ FeO (415.267)	60.96 (60.73)	5.36 (5.09)	19.11 (18.86)

TABLE 2—IR AND/OR ¹H NMR SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	δ ppm
2	1 605 (C=N), 1 690 (C=O), 3 340, 3 250, 3 150 (NH and NH ₂)	
4	1 710, 1 700 (C=O)	3.15 (2H, m, CH ₂ side chain), 3.4 (m, CH, side chain), 1.76–2.6 (8H, m, CH ₂ , cyclohexanone), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.1–7.6 (4H, m, ArH)
5	1 740, 1 750 (C=O)	
6	1 605 (C=N), 1 730 (C=O)	
8	1 600 (C=N), 1 720 (C=O)	3.6 (m, CH ₂ , cyclohexane), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.2 (2H, m, CH diazepine), 4.55 (9H, m, CH, ferrocene), 7.2–7.7 (9H, m, ArH)
10	1 650 (C=O), 1 735 (C=O)	
11	1 670 (C=O)	3.5 (2H, m, CH ₂ , cyclohexane), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.2 (2H, m, CH cyclohexane), 4.5 (9H, m, CH ferrocene), 7.2–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)
12	1 600 (C=N)	3.55 (2H, m, CH ₂), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.45 (9H, m, CH, ferrocene), 7.1–7.6 (4H, m, ArH)
13	1 620 (C=N)	3.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (9H, m, CH ferrocene), 5.6 (1H, s, olefinic), 7.1–7.8 (9H, m, ArH)

Ferrocenylsemicarbazone (2): Acetylferrocene (0.05 mol) was dissolved in pyridine (30 ml) and a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.05 mol) in water (5 ml) was added. After shaking for 15 min, the reaction mixture was left at room temperature (25–27°) for 5–7 days. The resulting solid product was filtered off and crystallised from acetic acid to get a brown-red crystals of 2 (Table 1).

2-[3-Oxo-1-(p-methoxyphenyl)-3-(1-ferrocenyl)]-cyclohexanone (4) and 2-[3-oxo-1-(p-methoxyphenyl)-3-(1-ferrocenyl)]tetralone (5): A mixture of 3a (0.01 mol) and cyclohexanone or α -tetralone (0.02 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with aqueous 50% sodium hydroxide (3 ml), then set aside at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice (50 g) and the separated

solid was filtered off and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) as pale yellow crystals of **4** and from ethanol as brown crystals of **5** (Table 1).

1,2-Benzodiazepines 6 and 8: To a solution of **4** (0.005 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) containing acetic acid (2 ml), was added hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) or phenylhydrazine (0.006 mol), and the mixture was heated under reflux for 4–5 h. After cooling, the mixture was poured into ice-cold water, and the solid separated was filtered off, dried and crystallised from aqueous ethanol to give a brown-red crystals of **6** and brown crystals of **8** (Table 1).

Michael condensation of 3a with acetophenone and/or 1,3-diphenylacetone. Formation of 10 and 11: A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and acetophenone or 1,3-diphenylacetone (0.015 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was treated with aqueous 20% sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml), and then set aside at room temperature for 5 days. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water, and the solid separated was filtered off, and crystallised from ethanol (three times) as brown crystals of **10** and brown-red crystals of **11** (Table 1).

Pyrimidotetrazole 12 and pyrimidopyrazole 13: A solution of **3a** (0.001 mol) and 5-aminotetrazole monohydrate or 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole (0.0011 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 18 h. The reaction mixture was left to stand over-

night, and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol as brown crystals of **12** and brown-red crystals of **13** (Table 1).

References

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